

Title:

Magician's Overwrite Sequence: A Digit-Based Divisibility System.

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Overview:

Magician's overwrite sequence is a sequence of numbers 1-9 being overwritten and placed by a repeating pattern.

Every digit, $d \in \{1, \dots, 9\}$, is placed every d -th position, overwriting any smaller digits in its position.

The resulting sequence has a period of 2520 terms.

Origin/name:

The name magician's overwrite sequence comes from how I thought of this pattern.

I was on a bus and was looking out the window. I saw a place that had magicians and was open every other day. I thought about how that would mean that the schedule would change weekly, one week the magician would work Monday the next Tuesday. I then got curious, if the magician worked at multiple places and wanted to make their schedule hard to predict then how could they do that. The idea of going to one place every other day, another once every 3 days, and another every 4 days, etc... arose from this thought, I then programmed it to simulate a schedule like that. The 'overwrite sequence' is based on how it functions.

first 200 terms:

1234567895161758191572185297161832791238171492187534195832161298
5614371912547618921752381974325817951618721915381654927812345918
3516729816173219527416189756123879145218159416783219173856149518
12571918

Equation:

$$a(n) = \max\{d \in \{1, \dots, 9\} : d|n\}$$

Equivalently, $a(n)$ is the largest integer $d \in [1, 9]$ such that d divides n .

Properties:

This sequence takes 2520 terms to repeat

$$a(n) = a(n+2520)$$

Because $2520 = \text{lcm}(1, \dots, 9)$

The frequency and approximate percentages of each number in a cycle, 2520 terms, is as follows

- 1 - 576 - 22.8%
- 2 - 288 - 11.4%
- 3 - 192 - 7.6%
- 4 - 144 - 5.7%
- 5 - 300 - 11.9%
- 6 - 180 - 7.1%
- 7 - 280 - 11.1%
- 8 - 280 - 11.1%
- 9 - 280 - 11.1%

Numbers in order of frequency from lowest to highest in a cycle of 2520 terms is as follows

4, 6, 3, 7, 8, 9, 2, 5, 1

Python code:

```
length=int(input('number of terms: '))
#change length to get that number of terms in the sequence

sequence=''
for i in range(length):
    sequence=sequence+'1'

def f(current_number):
    counter=0
    global sequence
    for i in range(length):
        counter=counter+1
        if counter==current_number:
            counter=0
            sequence=sequence[:i]+str(current_number)+sequence[i+1:]

for i in range(2,10):
    f(i)

print(sequence)

print(' ')

input()
```